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ACCORDING TO AYURVEDA, RASA DHATU AND ITS CORRELATION WITH PLASMA AND LYMPH_ ALITRATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Rasa Dhatu is the first dhatu to be formed in the order of sequential transformation. *Rasa Dhatu* is thenourishing body fluid that is continuously in circulation all over the body without any pause. During this continuous processof circulation *Rasa Dhatu* reaches each and every corner of the *Sharira* and gives nourishment, growth and does the maintenance of the body.*Rasa Dhatu* takes its origin from the *Hridaya* (heart) and *Dasha Rasavaha Dhamanis*. Anyimpact to it will lead to a death. Plasma is the liquid portion of blood, making up about 55% of total blood volume.It is a straw colored fluid in which blood cells (RBCs,WBCs, Platelets) float.Lymph is a clear fluid formed from plasma that leaks out of blood capillaries.

Rasa dhatu,plasma &lymph are having functional similarity that all are fluid ,flows all over the body , nourishes the body , keepImmunity and preserve the fluid balance.

Key Words:

Rasa Dhatu, Plasma,Lymph ,formation ,composition, function , proteins, circulation

INTRODUCTION:

LYMPH is a tissue fluid which is transparent, straw colored and alkaline in reaction. Lymph is drained by lymphatic vessels.

Right and Left lymphatic duct are the primary vessels of lymphatic drainage.

FORMATION OF LYMPH:

Lymph is formed from interstitial fluid derived from PLASMA or tissue fluid due to permeability of interstitial fluid into lymphatic capillaries.

When the arterial blood passes from arterial compartment to venous compartment through the tissue spaces a part of it permeates into tissue spaces forming the tissue fluid. The tissue fluid that enters into the lymphatic channels is called as Lymph.

COMPOSITION OF LYMPH:

Water 96% ,proteins, lymphocytes(W.B.C), FATS after intestinal absorption

FUNCTIONS OF LYMPH:

Drains excess interstitial fluid and returns to blood. Transport of absorbed fats(chyle). Helps in Immune Defence system. As it contains Lymphocytes and Antibodies. Lymph returns proteins, electrolytes, and water to blood from tissue spaces and help in maintenance of blood viscosity.

CIRCULATION OF LYMPH:

Through lymphatic vessels and lymph nodes.

PLASMA:

Forms the fluid compartments of the blood in which blood cells are suspended. The major portion of the blood is plasma.

COMPOSITION OF PLASMA:

Plasma contains 92% of water and 7% of plasma proteins, Electrolytes, Nutrients such as glucose, amino acids and lipids. Plasma Proteins are Albumin, Globulin, Fibrinogen. Plasma also contains Hormones and waste products.

Out of the rest of plasma 1% is composed of inorganic substances like sodium, calcium, potassium, bicarbonates and magnesium and organic substances like carbohydrates , amino acids , fatty acids , enzymes and other dissolved substances .

FUNCTIONS OF PLASMA:

Transport of nutrients, endocrine hormones, gases, and body waste products., Helps in Clotting(Fibrinogen) and Maintain pH and fluid balance.

CIRCULATION OF PLASMA:

Through blood vessels.

RASA DHATU:

According to the Ayurveda, in the human body, the one which is liquid in nature is called as Rasa dhatu. It is formed by the Ahara rasa.¹

Location of rasa dhatu is Heart. 24 dhamanias (Arteries) emerge from heart and circulating in entire body, nourishes all tissues.²

In fetal age Rasa dhatu originate from mother's Ahara rasa. Growth, nutrition, strength, and entire life of fetus depends on rasa dhatu.³

Rasa dhatu satisfies metabolic curges of an individual.⁴

Faeces and urine are the waste products of body. Its essence is rasa; this is circulated by Vyanavayu all over the body and nourishes all the dhatu.

Rasa dhatu is responsible for nutritional status of living body whether a person is thin or obese. This condition is applied only in adult life. In old age it sustains the life.⁵⁻⁶

Rasa dhatu works for nourishment of every space in living body. Rasa dhatu carries Ahara rasa to every body entity and keeps them fresh. Man is born from rasa; hence this rasa should be protected by all efforts.⁷

PRAMANA OF RASA DHATU –Rasa dhatu is 9 Anjali in measure.⁸

Physiology of Rasavaha Srotasa—Rasavaha srotasa represents various channels in the body which carry the nutrients responsible for the maintenance and nurture of the organism. Heart and attached ten dhamanias are principle organs of Rasavaha srotasa.⁹

Hence Rasavaha Srotasas are correlated with circulatory and Lymphatic system.

FORMATION OF RASA DHATU

Ahara which is made up of panchamahabhutas is of four types according to its use, six types of rasas, two or eight types of veeryas, or of many gunas when undergo digestion very minutest part of rasa dhatu is formed from that Ahara rasa. This shows extreme microform of rasa dhatu. It has Teja in it so it is penetrating in nature.¹⁰

After digestion of food two portions are separated. Saara and Kittabhaga. Here saarabhaaga is called Rasa. Rasa dhatu is first dhatu among seven dhatus. It is first formed in intra uterine life. Growth and nourishment is by food just like any other dhatu. Rasa dhatu is originated in fetal stage and is grown and nourished further all the way till death. In fetal stage it gets its origin through excellent part of ahara rasa of mother. Since fetus is deprived of hunger and thirst reflexes, and is dependent on mother, it grows on nourishment by mother. Rasa dhatu in the beginning is supplied with readymade nourishing material from excellent part of mother's Ahara rasa to fetus through umbilical cord. Ahara rasa is fluid, which circulates throughout the body, contains final absorbable products of digested food. This Ahara rasa reaches all dhatu channels and supplies nutrients for replenishing the dhatu, which undergoes catabolism.¹¹

Rasa dhatu is primarily made up of Jala Mahabhuta.

CIRCULATION OF RASA DHATU:-

Rasa dhatu spreads throughout the body simultaneously by the constant action of VyanaVata. While in movement, wherever it encounters obstructions due to anomalies of srotasa, disease precipitates there as rain is formed out of obstructed clouds in the sky.¹²

Rasa dhatu is situated in Hridaya(Heart) after being formed from Ahara rasa.¹³

To bring about circulation is main function of VyanaVata. It circulates entire body at a time. This act of circulation is ceaseless and done all the time. Rasa is forced in the entire body through sira; hence sira are said to originate from Heart.

VyanaVata is the key driving force behind circulation of Rasa to all parts of the body. Rasa dhatu moves sideways like sound, upwards like fire and downwards like water. 24 Rasa Dhamanies from heart will be responsible for circulating Rasa dhatu.

“Stanya” and “Raja” or “Artava” are considered to be up dhatu of Rasa. They are compared to breast milk and menstrual fluid respectively.¹⁴

PROPERTIES OF RASA DHATU: Drava (liquid), Sheeta(cold), Snigdha (unctuous), Sweet, Kaphaja in nature.

FUNCTIONS OF RASA DHATU:

1. Preenana nourishment.
2. Jeevana sustenance of life.
3. Tarpana satisfaction.
4. Poshana formation of subsequent dhatus.
5. Supports Raktadhatu formation.

DISEASES DUE TO DISORDERS OF RASA DHATU:

Anorexia, Vomiting sensation, Heaviness in body, Mental fatigue, Body ache, Fever, Darkness in front of eyes, Pallor, Blockage of srotasa, Impotency, Weakness, Emaciation, Agni mandya, Wrinkling of Skin, Graying of hair.¹⁵

DISEASES DUE TO DISORDERS OF PLASMA:

1. Plasma Protein Disorders
Hyperproteinemia, Hypoproteinemia, Multiple Myeloma
2. Clotting Factor Disorders (present in plasma)
Hemophilia, Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation
3. Electrolyte Imbalance In Plasma
Hyponatremia/Hypermnatremia, Hyperkalemia/Hypokalemia
4. Plasma Volume Disorders
Hypovolemia, Hypervolemia
5. Immune-Related Disorders
Autoimmune Diseases
6. Toxic and Metabolic Disorders
Accumulation of toxins (Uremia in kidney failure), High glucose in plasma (Diabetes Mellitus)

DISEASES DUE TO DISORDERS OF LYMPH:

Lymphedema, Elephantiasis, Lymphadenitis, Tuberculous Lymphadenitis, Hodgkin Lymphoma, Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma¹⁶

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION:

Rasa dhatu is the first formed dhatu from the Ahararasa during the time of fetal development, it contains all the nutrients which are necessary for the development of the body. According to above modern physiological studies Rasa dhatu's functions are similar to that of plasma, lymph and interstitial fluid, which also transports nutrients to the all tissues for their nourishment. Rasa dhatu, circulates throughout the body by Rasavaha Srotas which are similar to circulatory and lymphatic system. Diseases occurring in the body due to disfunctions of Rasa dhatu, Plasma and Lymph which are also resembles the same.

REFERENCES:

1. CharakaSamhita .SharirSthana 7/15
2. SushrutSamhita .SutraSthana 14/3
3. SushrutSamhita .ShariraSthana.3/33
4. Sushrut.Samhita .SutraSthana.15/5
5. Sushrut Samhita Sutra Sthana 15/32
6. Sushrut Samhita Sutra Sthana 14/3
7. SushrutSamhita .Sutra Sthana14/12
8. CharakaSamhita .SharirSthana 7/15
9. CharakaSamhita .VimanaSthana 5/10
10. SushrutSamhita .SutraSthana 14/3
11. CharakSamhita SutraSthana 28/4
12. CharakaSamhita .VimanaSthana15/36
13. SushrutSamhita .SutraSthana 14/3
14. CharakaSamhita .ChikitsaSthana15/17
15. CharakSamhita SutraSthana28/9
16. Essentials Of Medical Physiology Eighth Edition 2019, by Authors :K Sembulingam & Prema Sembulingam